

Green Business Strategies and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nairobi County

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Abstract

The main aim of the paper was to determine the effect of green business strategies and performance Small and Micro Enterprises. The study was anchored on competency theory. The study employed an explanatory research design in which the positivism paradigm was deployed. The study adopts. The target population was 102,821 firm owners. A sample of 383 respondents was selected using a stratified random sampling technique. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings showed that green business strategies (green purchasing and green packaging) significantly and positively affect the performance of small and medium enterprises. Thus, SMEs using green packaging and purchasing have a higher probability of increasing their performance that those without. Hence, there is a need for SMEs managers to exert pressure on green purchasing and packaging for better environmental performance. Specifically, the SMEs need to provide design specifications to suppliers that include environmental requirements for purchased items.

Keywords; Green Business Strategies, Green Purchasing, Green Packaging, Performance, Small And Medium Enterprises

1. Introduction

The varying degrees of political, social, and economic promulgation have initiated pressures related to environmental issues over the past few decades and this has caused companies to take these issues into greater consideration in their strategic and operational outlooks. The competitiveness of organizations has now gone beyond building quality products at low costs promptly (Sarkis et al., 2010), and now more focused on the conservation of natural resources and the environment in general.

Some companies are increasingly conscious of the need to reduce their environmental hazards but the spectrum of environmental initiatives they may undertake is very broad (Lefebvre et al., 2003). A small number of firms have already made significant progress in responding to the environmental challenge (Marcus and Willig, 1997) while others display a lacklustre attitude to internalize environmental issues and are still driven by compliance with legislation and risk avoidance (Lefebvre et al., 2003). This organisational attitude is also argued and supported by (Eccles et al., 2013) that during the last 20 years, a relatively small number of companies have integrated social and environmental policies in their business model and operations, on a voluntary basis.

Corporate responsibility, social and environmental issues are very critical for organizational competitiveness at strategic and operational levels (Porter and Kramer, 2006; Sarkis et al., 2010) and responses to them vary among firms in the same sector of economic activity and the same geographic region (Fisher and Schot, 1993; Handfield et al., 1997).

The environmental sustainability of our planet has a profound impact on the economy; and the pollution of air, soil and water is increasingly damaging the ecological system and this in turn may jeopardize the rate of economic growth. A sustainable economy can, therefore, be seen as essential for creating long term economic growth. The varying degrees of political, social, and economic promulgation has initiated pressures related to environmental issues over the past few decades and this has caused companies to take these issues into greater consideration in their strategic and operational outlooks. The competitiveness of organizations has now gone beyond building quality products at low costs promptly (Sarkis et al., 2010), and now more focused on the conservation of natural resources and the environment in general.

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York (2009), there are lots of benefits that the corporations can gain when they integrate the sustainability into their businesses such as efficient use of resources, return on investment, entering new markets, increasing the sales and revenues, enhancing the corporate image, product differentiation and enhanced competitive advantages. Chen et al. (2006) found that the competitive advantage of the firm depends on both the green product and green process innovation. There has been increasing emphasis on environment-friendly corporate activity in today's business world and many progressive companies are embracing green purchasing (Kamonya & Iraki, 2013). The rise in greenhouse emissions and pollution of the environments by firms has precipitated the need for organizations to realign their supply chain operations with a view of conserving the scarce resources. Green supply Chain Management (GSCM) is an approach to improve the performance of the process and products according to the requirements of the environmental regulations (Kamonya & Iraki, 2013).

As customers begin to demand environmentally friendly products, managers have been faced with the challenge of developing decisions that support the integration and coordination of environmental practices (Ondieki, 2012). Consequently, a sudden rise of environmental movements, legislations and concerns during the past decade have clearly outlined the need to address issues of environmental pollution accompanying industrial development together with business management, thus supporting the initiative of Green business Management (Ondieki, 2012).

However, while constituting a majority of businesses, SMEs lack, to a large extent, the awareness of their environmental impacts as well as the understanding that higher environmental performance can be a competitive advantage, despite the important role green procurement plays in ensuring environmental performance and public health and safety, most of the studies on this subject had been conducted in developed countries. Yet, not much research had been conducted in Kenya leading to the insufficient empirical literature on green procurement (Stephen & Helen, 2011). From the above it is evident that most studies have attempted to study determinants of green business and very few have assessed how green business strategies affect

performance. In this case, a study needs to be undertaken to specifically address the effect of green business strategies on the performance of the small and medium enterprises.

2. Theoretical framework

Hart (1995) argued that the RBV ignored challenges and constraints imposed by the natural environment, which should be important to consider in developing new resources and capabilities in order to deal with the acceleration of the scale and scope of human activity. He reasoned that past economic and organizational practices could not be continued as they would not continue to provide the same outcomes. Thus, he offered the natural resource-based view of the firm (NRBV) that posits future competitive advantage being rooted in “capabilities that facilitate environmentally sustainable economic activity” (p. 991). The NRBV has recently received support in research linking environmental sustainability practices related to SME activities to improved economic, operational and market performance (Vachon & Klassen, 2006, 2008). These authors note that SME processes have a direct impact on the natural environment, and practices to manage and reduce this impact can develop capabilities to improve performance.

The NRBV as proposed by Hart (1995) is built upon three interconnected strategies, two of which are focused on developed markets, pollution prevention, and product stewardship. Pollution prevention is concerned with reducing pollution, or the inefficient use of the material and human resources, in the manufacturing process. Like total quality management and lean production, pollution prevention means reducing waste which results in improved operational performance through better utilization of inputs, reduced cycle times and lower costs. Product stewardship entails integrating stakeholder perspectives into the product. It includes activities at every step in the value chain to focus on the entire lifecycle of a product from design to disposal. Implementing this strategy can enable a firm to develop a stronger reputation and competitive differentiation, both of which are market-based performance. Hart (1995) continues and additionally argues that these two strategies that bring improvements in operational and market performance ultimately result in enhanced cash flow and profitability or accounting-based performance for the firm.

NRBV of the firm as espoused by Touboulic and Walker (2015) involves reusability are a source of competitive advantage. The imperatives of sustainable development create opportunities for differentiation and increased market power. Inter-organizational resources as important as intra-organizational resources to stimulate supplier engagement with business strategies.

2.1. Hypothesis development (Review of Literature)

An extensive review of available literature reveals that there is very little research which has been conducted to probe why the practice of green purchasing is low or, alternatively, what motivates firms to adopt green purchasing activities (Chien and Shih, 2007; Hsu and Hu, 2008; Routroy, 2009; Srivastava, 2007; Zhu et al., 2007). Rao (2002) pointed to the dearth of research concerning supply chain environmental management even in developed countries where it first originated, even though it might prove to be a great solution to the greening industry in the South East Asian region. Walker and Phillips (2009) also pointed out that sustainable procurement is rising in many countries but knowledge remains limited. In Malaysia, there is a lack of empirical studies that investigates the mere existence of green supply chain initiatives in the country. With the exception of the (2002) study, no other study, which empirically investigates the extent of the existence of green purchasing in the general South East Asian region, has been found. Rao’s (2002) study only investigates the existence of green purchasing based on a sample of 52 companies taken from five countries (Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Singapore).

Green purchasing is defined as an environmentally-conscious purchasing initiative that tries to ensure that purchased products or materials meet environmental objectives set by the purchasing firm, such as reducing sources of waste, promoting recycling, reuse, resource reduction, and substitution of materials (Carter et al., 1998; Min and Galle, 2001; Zsidisin and Siferd, 2001). Green purchasing ensures that purchasing or supply chain managers consider the issue of sustainability in the purchasing of inputs, in addition to the traditional purchasing criteria of cost, quality, and delivery (Jimenez and Lorente, 2001; Kannan et al., 2008; Lambert and Cooper, 2000).

The adoption of green purchasing is one of the commonly accepted dimensions of GSCM practice. Tritoset al., (2013) states that buying an organization with a green supply chain initiative will pay attention to green practices of their suppliers, especially the small and medium-sized enterprises. In order to ensure that suppliers meet their environmental objectives, the buying firm may deploy collaboration-based activities that include training, environmental information sharing and joint research. Other organizations may adopt a less collaborative approach by simply demanding that their suppliers adopt environmental systems such as ISO 14001. External motivators and particularly, customer pressure are key drivers of the adoption of ISO 14001 Tritoset.al.,(2013), other aspects of green purchasing that have been discussed in the literature include the facilitation of recycling, reuse and resource reduction (Large & Thomsen, 2011; Diabat & Govindan, 2011). Studies have demonstrated that some organizations adopt compliance and evaluative approach to the GSCM practices of their suppliers. This involves evaluation of suppliers based on environmental criteria and a requirement for suppliers to develop and maintain some form of environmental management system (Sarkis, 2012) Green purchasing is an integration of environmental management into the purchasing function of an organization that attempts to ensure that the purchased material meet the environmental objectives set by the purchasing companies, such as promoting reusability, recycling, eliminating hazardous material from the product and substitution of material (Lokesh et .al 2017), it entails purchasing environmentally friendly raw materials without sacrificing the traditional purchasing criteria of product quality, cost and delivery time.

H₁: green purchasing significantly improves the performance of SMES

In order to meet the desires of environmentally aware consumers, companies need to work with a packaging solution company to create a custom design that is biodegradable, recyclable or reusable and streamlined. After all, consumers also want product packaging that is convenient and easy to use. Green packaging which is the explicit phenomenon in most instances has to do with suitable packaging that reduces environmental damage. Green packaging shows the reflection of environmental concerns in monetary terms which are intrinsic and transferable to the customer. Green communication fosters a positive image and conveys a business firm's concern towards the environment and the public (Ottman, 1998). Packaging provides benefits for companies as well as for consumers. For instance the surface of packaging serves as a communication platform for all kinds of information. This includes information such as product ingredients, price, usage data and other information that is relevant for consumers. Besides it serves marketing strategies as an instrument to increase the appeal of items to consumers resulting in less stock going unsold. The packaging does also controls the size and quantity of a product. (cf. referenceforbusiness.com, 2010) This is beneficial for companies in order to control inventory and manage the logistics of their product assortment. Moreover it improves the efficiency of product distribution and might therefore result in higher profit margins for companies.

Green packaging strategies become more complex and involve greater levels of relationship investment (Simpson and Samson, 2010). Within Green packaging practices, recoverable product environments, and the design of these products and materials, have become an increasingly important segment of the overall push in the industry towards environmentally conscious manufacturing and logistics for increased competitive advantage.

H₁: Green packaging significantly improves the performance of SMES

3. Materials and Methods

The study employed explanatory research design in the positivist paradigm, this paradigm was selected since the study employed the quantitative data to establish the direct and moderating effect of the variables under study. The concept of Positivism is directly associated with the idea of objectivism. This prompt for structured questionnaires and a larger number of the sample as compared to its counterpart paradigm. The study used explanatory research design to assess and establish the effect of behavioral factors, financial literacy on SME investment decisions in Nairobi County. A target population of 102,821 registered SMEs within Nairobi County was considered (Nairobi County, Ministry of Trade, 2016). Managers were selected purposively because they are in a superior position to comprehend investment decision issues of SMEs and in a position to give the correct data. Based on hyper-geometric distribution formulae, the study used a stratified and random sampling technique to select a sample size of 383. Similar studies (Morris, 2014) have adopted the hypergeometric distribution due to its ability to estimate sample sizes from large populations accurately. The study used questionnaires to collect primary data. The study adopted primary data collected from firms, or entrepreneurs through structured and unstructured questionnaires. Snapshots or cross-section method was used since data extracted only with the collection period. It employed a quantitative approach where quantitative techniques were utilized. Data collected were using 5 points Likert scale which was coded to numerical data using ordinal scales.

Reviewed literature demonstrates constructs testing for reliability accomplished by ascertaining the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Every one of the constructs was found to have a sufficient alpha value (> 0.6) (Hair *et al.*, 1998). Every item was measured using the five-point Likert scale. In evaluating the fit between the items and their constructs, the majority of the essential element loadings were more noteworthy than 0.5 and had no cross-loadings. The researcher ran a principal component analysis to identify patterns in data, and to express the data in such a way as to highlight their similarities and differences. The factor loadings for all items were above 0.5. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure value was above 0.5 hence acceptable. Also, the Bartlett's Test was significant.

The analysis involved the interpretation of survey data. Once completed, the study data were analyzed, which is the data collected from questionnaires using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, the mean and standard deviation were used mainly to summarize the data. Scale reliability and validity were assessed using Cronbach's coefficient alpha and factor analysis. Further, the study employed inferential statistics in the form of multiple regression and Pearson correlations analyses.

4. Findings and discussions

This presents the results and findings of the study according to the research objectives and hypotheses. The data were prepared for analysis by ensuring it met the minimum requirements for quantitative analysis. The questionnaires were therefore visually checked and tested for outliers for missing values and unfilled parts as well as for normality distribution.

Table 1; Univariate analysis

	Mean	Std. Deviation	SP	GP	Gpack
SP	4.02	0.54	1		
GP	3.96	0.76	.801**	1	
Gpack	4.02	0.52	.802**	.768**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

SP = *small and medium performance*
GP = *green purchasing*
Gpack = *green packaging*

Multivariate analysis

Results for multiple regression models showed that green purchase and green packaging explained 50.6 percent variation of performance of small and medium enterprises. This showed that considering a green purchase and green packaging, there is a probability of predicting the performance of small and medium enterprises by 50.6% (R squared =0.506). Finally, the study findings in the table indicated that the above discussed coefficient of determination was significant as evidence of the F ratio of 147.606 with p value 0.000 <0.05 (level of significance).

The first hypothesis stated that green purchase has a significant effect on the performance of small and medium enterprises. Nonetheless, the study findings showed that green purchase has a positive and significant effect on the performance of small and medium enterprises basing on $\beta_1 = 0.156$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) implying green purchase has a significant effect on the performance of small and medium enterprises. The hypothesis is therefore accepted. In corroboration with the findings, the study by Muma et al., (2014) established that there is a positive relationship between Green purchasing, and reverse logistics and environmental performance. On the same note, Al Khattb et al., (2015) proved that Green Supply chain management such as Green Purchasing, affected the environmental marketing performance.

The second specific objective of the study was to establish the effect of green packaging on procurement performance in a devolved system of government in Kenya. The findings in Table 2 show that green packaging has a positive and significant effect on the performance of small and medium enterprise $\beta_2 = 0.244$, $p = 0.004$ meaning that increasing green packaging by 1 unit would increase procurement performance by 0.244 units. The findings agree with Simpson and Samson (2010) that green packaging strategies become more complex and involve greater levels of relationship investment within green packaging practices, recoverable product environments, and the design of these products and materials, have become an increasingly important segment of the overall push in the industry towards environmentally conscious manufacturing and logistics for increased competitive advantage

Table 2: OLS results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	SE	Beta	t	Sig.	correlation
(Constant)	2.596	0.138		18.847	0	
Green purchasing	0.103	0.05	0.156	2.073	0.039	0.595*
Green packaging	0.127	0.044	0.244	2.921	0.004	0.631**
R	0.712a					
R-Square	0.506					
Adjusted R-Square	0.501					
Std. The error of the Estimate	0.241					
F	147.606					
Sig.	0.000b					

a Dependent Variable: Procurement performance

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

5. Conclusion

The firm cooperates with its suppliers for environmental objectives through sharing ideas. Furthermore, the firm does auditing on environmental suppliers' internal management and it ensures that it only deals with suppliers with ISO1400 certification. As well, the firm cooperates with customers for both cleaner production and green packaging. Green purchasing which entails cooperating with suppliers to develop environmentally sustainable products had a positive and significant influence on supply chain performance. The results suggest that the attainment of GSCM is a collaborative effort between the firm and its supply chain partners in aspects such as sharing ideas on environmental objectives and ensuring that there are cleaner production and green packaging. It is therefore easier for the manufacturing firms to audit its suppliers and choose one that complies with ISO1400 certification since there is close interaction in the supply chain. Further, the study found green packaging on the performance of small and medium enterprises. Thus, the study infers that the packaging product using green product enhances the performance of small and medium enterprises.

6. Recommendation

Since green purchasing enhances the performance of small and medium enterprises, it is recommended or SMEs to exert pressure on their suppliers for better environmental performance. Specifically, the SMEs need to provide design specifications to suppliers that include environmental requirements for purchased items. Besides, there is a need for the firms to do auditing on environmental suppliers' internal management and ensure that it cooperates with customers for both cleaner production and green packaging. This study expands our knowledge on the effects of green purchases on the performance of small and medium enterprises. Though this study has fulfilled its aim and objectives, and there are several areas for additional studies and empirical research, given the limitations of the research. The methodology that has been chosen to achieve the research objectives was limited to questionnaires. As such, future research could build on this study by examining the effects of the green performance of small and medium enterprises in different sectors and industries in both a qualitative and quantitative way. Also, a replication of this research on different industries would provide data for comparison.

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